

Social Media Regulation: Political Polarization

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Abstract

In the last few years, political polarization has surged exponentially in the US. Despite recent research revealing that this growing polarization is harming democracy, there is hardly any agreement on its principal causes. This observational study sought to investigate polarization in multi-issue contexts by asking a series of behavioral questions that measures the degree to which humans have become polarized. I specifically sought to learn how political affiliation and ideologies have evolved relative to social media use. My investigation revealed that individuals are more likely to hold majority opinions when abstract issues are presented as predetermined choices. Notably, I found that Democrats and Republicans move toward opposite extremes of their viewpoints and opinions. Independents, however, fluctuated slightly between depolarized and polarized viewpoints. These findings indicate that society is exceedingly susceptible to partisan influencers on social media and that political content is a crucial determinant of whether a social network will polarize users and the degree of polarization they experience. Recognizing the origins of polarization is essential for determining how to tackle the adverse effects it has on society as a whole.

Introduction

Social media is a persistent Internet-based platform for mass personal communication that facilitates perceptions of user interactions and gets much of its value from user-generated material (Carr & Hayes, 2015). Some examples of social media platforms are Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Snapchat, and LinkedIn. These platforms are ubiquitous in people's lives and have fundamentally altered the nature of everyday relationships. Many people no longer have political dialogues only with people in their surrounding communities, but rather with strangers from all over the world; society no longer shares only a few reliable sources of media, but absorbs and exchanges immensely different sources of information with just a few clicks.

Social media, unsurprisingly, has grown in power and has had a huge influence on humans' political and civic life. For example, it has led to the establishment of online echo chambers- spaces where users are more likely to encounter like-minded people who reinforce their perspectives- as well as the propagation of misinformation. A recent study limited to Twitter claimed that fake news travels faster than real news (Cinelli et al., 2021). Fake news can negatively affect society because it leads to a division in beliefs or opinions, known as polarization. The polarization currently being experienced both within and among nations undercuts efforts to deal with critical issues facing societies (Kelly, 2021). An understanding of how polarization has affected society and how social media plays a role is essential. There are two types of polarization to be explored: ideological and political. Political polarization occurs when the dispersion of the political views of Democrats and Republicans goes toward ideological extremes. Ideological polarization is how much individuals consistently hold conservative or liberal views on several subjects.

The paradox is evident: social media may be utilized for both benevolent and malicious purposes. Digital platforms can be extremely lucrative enterprises that link customers and other market participants in new and innovative ways. They produce powerful positive feedback loops known as network effects- which is when a service gains additional value as more people use it- then monetize them by selling advertisements. However, what transpired at the US Capitol on January 6th shows how social media platforms may have drawbacks since they were the main sources where people conspired. Indeed, social media has produced billions of dollars. However, these platforms have also caused false information to spread about elections, vaccinations, and public health issues, and manipulated digital material for political ends. The purpose of this project is to explore the extent to which political content in social media causes bias and polarization and to determine if social media regulation can alleviate this problem.

Literature Review

The flow of information is never-ending in modern society. Whether through search engines, televisions, or digital devices, humans have access to virtually any information they need. Presumably, with the introduction of social networks, the Internet has fostered new forms of online and offline political activity, including grassroots anti-establishment movements, which in turn institutionalized and fed back into the mainstream electoral process (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). Media reporting plays an important role in the political process. In fact, the media is a tool that empowers humans everywhere to make informed decisions about what they should do. In a way, it brings humanity together by keeping everyone informed on the latest events and occurrences. With the addition of social media into the news stream, society has become familiar with the platforms and has formed their beliefs and opinions on them. 43% of Democrats ages 18 to 29 say social media has a mostly negative effect on the way things are going, compared with

about 76% of Republicans (Auxier, 2020). It can be seen that Republicans are heavily biased toward the belief in the negative effects of social media, while Democrats don't seem to see any problems with it. This is important to note because the preconceived beliefs of humans heavily influence the ways they interact with the world and view things. Preconceived beliefs are especially important in politics because they further fuel polarization when people search to affirm wrong beliefs, and they lead to a search for confirmation bias. What's more, is that society can especially become influenced by a social media post from a prominent figure. Presidents, celebrities, and even local community members use these platforms to get their messages instantly across to millions of people. These posts then translate into primary sources for news articles and become a main talking point for political discussions. Yet, the ease of instantaneously reaching millions may prove to be problematic. Studies of the influence of fake news sites during elections, demonstrate that fake news was both widely shared in the 2016 campaign period and heavily tilted in favor of Donald Trump. It shows that Democrats and Republicans are both about 15% more likely to believe ideologically aligned headlines, and this effect is substantially stronger for users in homogenous social media networks (Tucker et al., 2018). False news is dangerous to society because it proliferates news media and leads people to believe the information as fact when it is not. Social media is an outlet for people across the globe to strengthen political conversation through a free exchange of ideas. Then again, this freedom may become a problem because users' privilege to publish any political information they choose brings in extremist ideologies. Recently, the radicalism of social media posts has reached unparalleled heights, whether it's through content that supports terrorism, racism, or misogyny. As more and more humans become exposed to alarming ideas, they become easily swayed by whatever posts they are surrounded by which is known as group polarization. Group

polarization occurs when members of a group decide on actions that are more extreme than their original inclination. Thus, social media plays a crucial role in the divergence of political ideologies amongst Americans.

Political polarization is on the rise across the globe, especially in the United States. It can be detrimental to democracy, increasing the centralization of power, congressional gridlock, and making citizens less satisfied (Sikorski et al., 2021). The main principles of democracy focus on giving power to the people. That said, when humans are divided, how will they make decisions that will benefit society as a whole? As the public becomes disconnected, democracy is at risk. How societies perceive polarization is just as important in highlighting how polarization has affected political parties. A belief that members of society share similar values and norms undergirds social trust and trust in fellow citizens—so-called generalized social trust—acts as the social glue that binds people together in harmony and for the common good, (Lee, 2022). Society is generally aware of the division that is prevalent in American society. Still, there is a general trust in others for the common good of democracy, even though it has been declining in recent years. The chief aspect of social media that can be attributed to a growing division is echo chambers. Social media users do not get exposed to content exposing differing opinions, leading to narrowmindedness. A survey has found that using like-minded partisan media in the US can increase anger toward the ‘other side’ and make people more willing to share political information on social media (Arguedas et al., 2022). Negative emotions towards other parties lead to turmoil in communities. Protests and conflicts may arise from built-up anger against opposing viewpoints, which further divides America. Echo chambers further intensify this issue because they fuel anger when there is disagreement across parties. As the gap between political parties widens, partisans tend to go to the extreme to ensure their party is supported. Partisans

frequently ignore the viewpoints of the other party and only reference evidence that supports their position. Political disagreements require civil discourse, which can be achieved by becoming informed about all sides of an issue before developing an opinion. In addition, since people are constantly surrounded by the opinions of others on social media, they can't form a rational opinion of their own, leading to a groupthink scenario. Groupthink is a form of thinking where individuals in groups often accept an idea or judgment that they believe to be held by the group, regardless of whether or not they believe it to be accurate. In summary, political echo chambers exacerbate polarization which undermines US democracy.

Misinformation on social media has become an issue because it leads to unconscious compliance and partisan action. The proliferation of a fact or norm is valuable to the extent that it changes behaviors, and this value can accrue to both private entities and the state alike (Fagan, 2022). Social media has changed the social norms of society. The dissemination of endless information allows new generations to challenge traditional beliefs and bring in a new wave of awareness of issues in society, such as the “woke” movement. However, the problem of false information has cast a shadow over the growth of social media, especially in light of the 2016 US Presidential election, in which false information was believed to have influenced the outcome. People with malicious intentions on social media raise concerns because the spread of misinformation intensifies American national conflicts. For example, if users see fake content that is upsetting, it could lead them to make dangerous or influenceable decisions, like violent protests or a change of a vote. Moreover, individuals frequently use social media with the intention of pleasure-seeking, which lessens their propensity to verify the information they consume. Repeated exposure to material that supports their preexisting opinions makes it seem more credible and shareable. Confirmation bias is the driving force behind the aforementioned

echo chamber phenomenon (Muhammed, 2022). The predisposition to embrace information that confirms current ideas while ignoring alternative viewpoints and perspectives other than one's own is known as confirmation bias. Therefore echo chambers and misinformation work together to validate the preexisting beliefs of individuals and amplify the polarization they experience.

Social media regulation is the process of applying a variety of unique techniques to moderate systems to carry out predetermined policy objectives. Social media platforms need to take more responsibility for their impact on the world, lest they run the risk of continuing to damage essential common resources for information and commerce—the internet itself, and user trust in digital content (Cusumano et al., 2022). Social media platforms are private businesses that pursue managerial objectives such as profit, brand recognition, civic responsibility, and benevolent regulatory frameworks. In other words, social media platforms have capitalistic tendencies, where their main focus is making a profit from humans interacting with their sites. Therefore, these companies seem to disregard the growing political divide facilitated by their platforms. Rather than fixing this issue, social media companies are fueling it by creating even more algorithms and features that further personalize social media users' feeds. Introducing legislation to regulate extremist political content could be a possible solution to political polarization. Yet, under current United States law, social media platforms like Facebook can continue to operate and implement harmful algorithms because there is little congressional oversight on these issues (Denny, 2022). There may be some gray areas concerning governmental interference with social media regulation because of the First Amendment. However, social media companies should be encouraged to self-regulate. The first step to self-regulation could be getting rid of echo chamber algorithms to allow users to see all points of view, foster an open mind, and learn how to deal with opposing opinions. To this end, social

media companies should be held accountable by managing content to unite Americans in their tolerance of other worldviews.

Methods

An Institutional Review Board reviewed and approved this project to verify that the methods employed were ethical. To begin this experiment, I went to Google Forms and created a new survey. I formulated questions that would be beneficial for determining participants' political affiliation, beliefs, main sources for news, and social media feeds. Many questions were similar to that from <https://www.pewresearch.org/politics/quiz/political-typology/>. I then input them into the survey (Attached Appendix A). In terms of the questions asked, I made sure to include demographic questions such as grade, age, and gender. I then prompted participants to take a political personality survey at <https://www.politicalpersonality.org/test/>. I chose this website because it's been vetted with questions and it's proven to give reliable questions with reliable data. I included this question to gauge what their ideologies were, then compare it to their political affiliation which was the next question. Next, I asked where people get their news from to determine if social media is a valid source for news in my population, and I also asked which social media source they use most. Another notable question asked was whether or not they believe America is divided. It was important to ask this because it suggests whether there is an issue in modern society or not. Finally, in a free-response question, I asked what type of content should be censored on social media. I asked this because the opinions of participants are important in my research. I gathered survey participants who are a representative sample of the population parameter: teens and adults aged 16-60 years old from Melbourne, Florida. I chose this sample because I live in this city thus I would be able to access more participants. Also, the average age in this city is 41.4 years old so these participants are centered around this age. I gave

my participants a consent form to sign before taking the survey (Appendix B). When I received the consent forms, I emailed the survey link to the participants. After receiving all responses, I gathered the data into a Google Spreadsheet. I used Google Spreadsheets because Google Forms had a function to transfer the data from Google Forms to Google Spreadsheets. To take statistical tests such as correlations and z-tests, I assigned numerical values to each variable. The numbers ranged from 0-7. I assigned answers of “yes” to the number 1, and answers of “no” to the number 2. Other numbers ranged depending on the answer types. For instance, political affiliation was assigned as follows: democrat=1, independent=2, republican=3. Then, I took the correlations and determined the strongest correlations. The strongest correlations were the ones that were closest to +1 or -1. After completing the correlations, I began a one-sample z-test for proportions to determine if there was statistical significance. I derived the null hypotheses from Pew Research and created my own alternative hypotheses. One of my null hypotheses was derived from <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2021/04/07/partisan-differences-in-social-media-use-show-up-for-some-platforms-but-not-facebook/> (Attached Appendix A). I chose this website because it has reliable data and it’s a reliable source to which I can compare my data to. The significance level of .05 was assigned and the conditions were checked for normality as these are the prerequisites to completing significance tests. I used the formula: $Z = (p - P_0) / SE$, then plugged in the values and determined the p-value. I then compared the p-value to the significance level of .05 to determine whether or not the null hypothesis should be rejected. If the p-value was less than the significance level, then the null hypothesis was rejected. If the null hypothesis was rejected, I assumed there is a direct relationship between the two variables. If the p-value was greater than the significance level, then the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. If I failed to reject the null hypothesis, I assumed

that the sample did not provide sufficient evidence to conclude that an effect exists. Lastly, I placed the data in charts and drew conclusions.

Results & Discussion

Society lives in polarized times in both media feeds and daily lives. Society is politically and ideologically polarized, and more partisan than ever. Whether it's a deteriorating democracy or an exacerbation of social tensions, political polarization leaves negative impacts on society. Given the growing attention this topic is receiving in the US, there is a need for further study deeper into this topic that explores the components that lead to this phenomenon. Political polarization has been linked to social media, and many experts contend that this is because of the echo chambers that social media platforms' algorithmic designs can produce. However, my observational study sheds new light on this issue. My research raises the possibility that political polarization may be indicated by social media use. My findings also showed that Americans of all ages, particularly those of younger generations, are ideologically inconsistent as seen in Figure 1 (all graphs can be found in Appendix C). According to data converted into percentages gathered from survey responses from an array of social media users, people who use social media for politics are more likely to display ideological homogeneity than people who use traditional news sources that provide a varied pattern of news consumption. Only 17% of participants had consistently liberal views, whereas 25% identified as Democrats. Only 6% had consistently conservative views, whereas 31% identified as Republicans.

Figure 1

After I took z-tests for proportions, there were only five statistically significant results. Various Pew Research-derived hypotheses on the usage of social media as a source of news and opinions, as well as attitudes regarding social media content regulation, were examined in this instance using the z-tests. There was convincing evidence that the true proportion of Democrats that derive news from social media was greater than 77% with a p-value of about 0.000001. The fact that most Democrats depend on social media to stay informed might have repercussions on the political situation in the country. High social media use causes ideological homogeneity, which is seen in the peak in liberal views in Figure 1. Furthermore, my research indicates that social media sites like Facebook and Instagram significantly influence the political opinions of the people who use them. There was convincing evidence that the true proportion of Democrats that derive their news from Instagram was greater than 49% with a p-value of about .000001. Similarly, there was convincing evidence that the true proportion of Republicans that derive their news from Facebook was greater than 69% with a p-value of .00001. The January 6th Capitol attack is a case in point where Facebook was the primary platform used by the rioters- who were

predominantly Republican- to conspire and disseminate false information. Additionally, the z-test results show that there is an important disparity in views regarding social media regulation between Republicans and Americans. There was convincing evidence that the true proportion of Republican adults who believe social media content should not be regulated was greater than 70% with a p-value of .0065. There was convincing evidence that the true proportion of Americans who believe social media should be regulated was greater than 91% with a p-value of about 0.0000001. This finding is quite intriguing as it reveals a deep divide in the perception of social media regulation between the two groups. The importance of social media in influencing society’s political opinions is therefore highlighted by these findings, which also underscore the need for a more thorough knowledge of how it affects society. These data can all be found in Figure 2.

Figure 2

This study also yielded notable correlations between various factors and beliefs about social media and politics, as seen in Figure 3. I found a high positive correlation between the male gender and posting political content on social media, indicating that males are more likely to post political content. This finding could be explored further to understand the reasons behind this gender difference and how it impacts political discourse on social media. I also found a moderately strong, positive correlation between political engagement and belief in social media regulation, suggesting that those who are politically active are more likely to support social media regulation, possibly because they see it as a way to address the growing concerns about fake news and misinformation. Lastly, I found a moderately strong, positive correlation between belief in fake news and belief in censorship, suggesting that those who believe there is fake news also support social media regulation. Social media regulation could be a solution that 91% of participants believed would bridge the growing divide. Thus, the study provides valuable insights into the complex relationship between social media, politics, and polarization, and highlights the need for further regulation in this area. It also emphasizes the need for additional studies on the intricate connections between political polarization, social media use, and the larger socio-political environment in which these trends occur. Humans can create more effective ways to encourage greater political moderation, lower social tensions, and establish a more robust democratic society by having a better knowledge of the elements that lead to political polarization.

Figure 3

Correlations

Conclusion

The study revealed that social media is fostering political animosity and ideological homogeneity. Individuals are more likely to hold majority political opinions when abstract issues are presented as predetermined choices. Interestingly, I found that Democrats and Republicans moved toward opposite extremes of viewpoints and opinions. Independents, however, fluctuated slightly between polarized and depolarized viewpoints. Compared to 2016, political animosity has drastically grown. According to Pew Research (2020), 77% of Americans believed that America was divided, compared to my study, 89% of Americans believed America was divided. The introduction of free-response questions greatly revealed the polarization caused by social media: basic stereotypes were frequently cited as answers. The free-response questions were also interesting in that the outliers of the group provided insightful answers that were crucial to my research. Even though there was an “other” answer choice that would allow participants to place their opinions, most of them chose the predetermined answer options. This is important because

it shows that there's a lack of individuality and a stigma when it comes to people sharing opinions that are different from the rest. My findings also imply that political content is a crucial determinant of whether social media will polarize users and the degree of polarization they experience. In particular, political content that is extremist or fake has the most impact on humans. Understanding the origins of polarization is crucial for understanding how to mitigate the detrimental effects it has on society. My findings imply that this trend in political polarization may not only be caused by political content but also it may be caused by polarized partisans; whether it be individuals who felt that America is divided or those who claimed that their friendships were impacted by politics. Moreover, I found that Democrats that use social media for news were more likely to have the same ideologies, while Republicans were more likely to use Facebook for news. The charts presented in this work serve as a platform for additional research into the factors that lead to political polarization through analytical means. Social media regulation of extremist views must be implemented to alleviate this issue. Whether companies self-regulate or get rid of echo chambers, some sort of rules should be in place to prevent social media from harming public interest and democracy.

The approach of this study was created to encourage more research. Eventually, future studies on this subject should not only aim to discover causes but also address these causes. Though my research produced more questions than answers, further investigations may explore the prevalence and types of political discussions that occur online. This would further aid in gauging how polarization is occurring from social media. Eventually, studying political and ideological polarization should aim to not only pinpoint its root causes but also provide solutions to them. Though social media regulation could be a solution, different solutions should be identified for a greater impact. Since partisans were shown to have a significant influence on

group polarization, it seems logical that content created to depolarize social media might also have significant impacts. This could be tested by bringing together a group of people with the same political affiliation, then showing them extremist political content or fake news, and allowing them to deliberate this content. The degree to which this content polarized the group could then be measured and compared to a group that was shown depolarizing content.

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Appendix A

Social Media Regulation: Political Polarization

The purpose of this survey is to determine if social media posts influence political beliefs and if social media posts should become regulated.

Email:

Name:

Age:

Grade:

Gender:

Please take this short Political Personality Quiz: <https://www.politicalpersonality.org/test/>

Which personality did you get from the quiz?

- Astute logician
- Civic Observer
- Freedom Steward
- Growth Capitalist
- Justice Warrior
- Social Guardian
- Stalwart Nationalist
- Utopian Virtuoso

What is your political affiliation?

- Democrat
- Republican
- Independent

Where do you get most of your news from? (1=most used source, 4=least used source)

- Social Media
- Internet
- TV
- Radio

What social media platform do you get news from the most? Rank from most used to least (1=most used, 7=least used)

- Youtube
- Instagram
- Twitter
- Facebook

Linkedin
Whatsapp
Tiktok

Do you get bipartisan feeds or partisan feeds?

Bipartisan
Partisan

Do you consider yourself to be politically engaged/active?

Yes
No
Other

Have you ever posted any political content on social media?

Yes
No
Other

Do politics play a role in your friendships?

Yes
No
Other

Do you believe America is divided

Yes
No
Other

Do you consider mainstream media to be fake news?

Yes
No
Other

Which news channel do you prefer to watch on TV and why? (Fox news, CNN, etc)

Long answer text

Have you ever heard of alternative social media sites such as: BitChute, Gab, Gettr, Parler, Rumble, Telegram, or Truth Social?

Yes

No
Other

Have you ever used alternative social media sites for news such as: BitChute, Gab, Gettr, Parler, Rumble, Telegram, or Truth Social?

Yes
No
Other

What type of content on social media do you believe should be censored?

Long answer text

Null hypothesis derived from: <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2021/04/07/partisan-differences-in-social-media-use-show-up-for-some-platforms-but-not-facebook/>

Appendix B

Human Informed Consent Form

Instructions to the Student Researcher(s): An informed consent/assent/permission form should be developed in consultation with the Adult Sponsor, Designated Supervisor or Qualified Scientist.

This form is used to provide information to the research participant (or parent/guardian) and to document written informed consent, minor assent, and/or parental permission.

- When written documentation is required, the researcher keeps the original, signed form.
- Students may use this sample form or may copy ALL elements of it into a new document.

If the form is serving to document parental permission, a copy of any survey or questionnaire must be attached.

Student Researcher(s): Hana Saleh

Title of Project: Social Media Regulation: Political Polarization

You are being asked to volunteer to participate in this science project. If you would like to participate, please sign in the appropriate area below.

Purpose of the project:
to determine if social media posts influence in political beliefs and if does social media post require censorship

If you participate, you will be asked to:
take a political preference quiz online and answer questions on a survey about where you get your news from

Time required for participation:
5-10 minutes total

Potential Risks of Study:
anxiety

Benefits:
to help better understand the role social media posts play in political beliefs of teenagers and adults

How confidentiality will be maintained:
no names will be used; numbers will be assigned

If you have any questions about this study, feel free to contact: Mary Schropp

Adult Sponsor/QS/DS Mary Schropp Phone/email schropp.mary@brevardschools.org

Voluntary Participation:

Participation in this study is completely voluntary. There will be no negative consequences if you decide not to participate, stop participating, or refuse to answer any question.

By signing this form I am attesting that I have read and understand the information above and I freely give my consent/ assent to participate or permission for my child to participate.

Adult Informed Consent or Minor Assent Date Reviewed & Signed _____
(mm/dd/yy)

Research Participant Printed Name _____ Signature: _____

Parental/Guardian Permission (if applicable) Date Reviewed & Signed _____
(mm/dd/yy)

Parent/Guardian Printed Name _____ Signature _____

Appendix C

Ideological Views

Statistical Significance

Correlations

